

1 **Xist controls histone acetyl-lysine reader function through CECR2.**

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6 We studied total transcription in cells with engineered, specific deletions in the gene encoding Xist in
7 human cells. We demonstrate here that control of *CECR2* is an authentic function of the Xist non-coding
8 RNA. *CECR2* bound MECP2, which was likely involved in its chromatin reading function. Xist controls
9 histone acetyl-lysine reader function through *CECR2*.

10 Citations

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